

MODELLING THE IMPACT OF EXTERNAL DEBT ON THE MACROECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

The factors that determine the amount of external public debt are considered. The factors of influence of the external debt on the macroeconomic development of Ukraine are estimated. The stages of building a VAR model are considered. A comparison of the data generated by the model with the actual historical data is carried out. The forecasted values of individual macroeconomic indicators according to the VAR model (2) are presented. The dynamic of the macroeconomic indicators of Ukraine, which have interdependent relations with the public debt, is presented. The existence of cause-and-effect relationships between the ratio of general government sector debt to GDP of Ukraine and a number of macroeconomic indicators, mainly with time lags of 1 and 2, is revealed. The obtained results indicate an expected downward trend in the indicator in the next 5 quarters. It is determined that an increase in the share of external debt in GDP should be expected.

Keywords: debt, external public debt, macroeconomic development, model, impact.

Introduction. Public debt management involves the process of creating and implementing strategic mechanisms for influencing the public debt, which ensure the possibility of attracting the necessary amount of financing, achieving target spending indicators at an acceptable level of risk, as well as achieving any other goals that the government sets for itself, for example, development and maintaining an efficient market of government securities. From the point of view of the macroeconomic context of public policy, the government must ensure the stability of the level and rate of growth of the public debt, which can be serviced under various circumstances, adhering to the target indicators of costs and risks.

Literature Review. Considering aspects of the impact of external debt on the macroeconomic development of countries of the world, it can be argued that there are many models that describe this impact. Representatives of the scientific community [1–10] and others study the impact of external debt on the macroeconomic development of countries of the world. However, certain aspects of these issues have not yet been studied in detail.

The article is aimed at developing a model and validating the results of the impact of external debt on the macroeconomic development of Ukraine.

Research Finding. The amount of external public debt depends on many factors, including key economic indicators, namely: gross domestic product (GDP), volume and dynamic of exports, volume and dynamic of imports, value and dynamic of the exchange rate, the state of the balance of payments, the inflation rate, the Central Bank's discount rate and its derivatives, state budget deficit, political stability (instability), etc. It should be borne in mind that the external debt indicator is not static; its amount may vary depending on many factors, including changes in the taxation regime, changes in regulatory policies, changes in foreign economic conditions (for example, changes in the volume of foreign demand for export goods), changes in the

economic environment, etc. All these changes may affect the amount of other macroeconomic indicators and, in turn, the amount of external public debt.

Based on the above, the article assesses the factors of influence of external debt on the macroeconomic development of Ukraine on the basis of the following indicators: the ratio of general government sector debt to GDP; debt service as a percentage of total state budget expenditures; consumer price index; real effective exchange rate index; foreign direct investments; the volume of imports; and the political stability index. The existence of statistical significance of causal relationships is proved using the Granger test and a forecast model of the public debt to GDP ratio is built on the basis of the ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) model.

The procedure for building a VAR model includes the following steps: analysis of time series characteristics; causality test (existence of relationships between variables); test for stationarity of time series; transformation of time series into stationary ones (if necessary); search for the optimal model order; data preparation; model development and estimation; forecasting data for future periods based on the model and carrying out the transformation of the results (if necessary).

Modern economic research is based on the use of econometric models of various types. In our case, the indicators under study change over time. That is why the basis of modelling is the choice among those models that are designed to model time series. The purpose of the modelling is to forecast future values of the indicator under study. In addition, based on the obtained results, it is possible to draw conclusions and recommendations for managerial decisions in the field of macroeconomic development of the country. Two broad approaches have been developed for modelling time series data: the time domain approach and the frequency domain approach.

Among the list of models, the VAR (Vector Autoregression) model was selected, which is used to study the dynamic of macroeconomic indicators and their relationship with external public debt. The chosen model

allows to calculate the impact of changes in one indicator on other indicators, which can be useful for forecasting future external debt, as well as to draw conclusions about the impact on macroeconomic development.

Models are developed and the results of the impact of external debt on Ukraine's macroeconomic development are validated. A comparison of the data generated

by the model with actual historical data is presented below (Figure 1). The forecasted values of individual macroeconomic indicators according to the VAR (2) model for the period 2021–2023 are shown in Figure 2. The dynamic of Ukraine's macroeconomic indicators that have interdependent connections with public debt (for the period 2015–2021) is shown in Figure 3.

General government sector debt to GDP of Ukraine, %

Debt servicing to total state budget expenditures of Ukraine, %

Consumer price index

Index of the real effective exchange rate of the hryvnia to the US dollar

Foreign direct investments

Imports

Political stability index

— Actual data
 - - - Model data

Fig. 1. Comparison of actual data with the model values of the VAR model (2)

General government sector debt to GDP of Ukraine, %

Debt servicing to total state budget expenditures of Ukraine, %

Consumer price index

Index of the real effective exchange rate of the hryvnia to the US dollar

Political stability index

Fig. 2. Forecasted values of individual macroeconomic indicators according to the VAR model (2) for the period 2021–2023.

Consumer price index

Index of the real effective exchange rate of the hryvnia to the US dollar

Fig. 3. The dynamic of Ukraine's macroeconomic indicators that have interdependent relations with public debt (for the period 2015–2021)

The existence of cause-and-effect relationships between the ratio of general government sector debt to GDP of Ukraine and a number of macroeconomic indicators, mainly with time lags 1 and 2, was revealed which allows to proceed to building an econometric model. The obtained results show an expected downward trend in the indicator over the next 5 quarters. However, actual verification of the model in modern conditions of military operations is impossible. This is due to a catastrophic drop in GDP and a rapid increase in foreign aid to Ukraine from allies, some of which comes under extended funding programmes. Under these conditions, the share of external debt in GDP is expected to grow.

Conclusions. A model of the influence of external debt on the macroeconomic development of Ukraine was developed using the VAR model methodology. The obtained system of 5 equations allows to form qualitative forecast estimates that confirm their reliability in retrospect, and the model itself can be used to develop practical measures of public debt management policy, forecasting related macroeconomic indicators and implementing measures for public administration of economic development of Ukraine.

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